

Synthesis and Properties of Coordination Compounds with Tetraisopropoxyaluminate as a Bidentate Ligand

R. C. MEHROTRA and JAGVIR SINGH

Chemical Laboratories, University of Delhi, Delhi-110 007

A large number of double isopropoxides of alkali metals, alkaline earth metals, gallium, indium, scandium, yttrium, lanthanons, zirconium, hafnium, thorium, niobium, and tantalum with aluminium have been synthesised. The observed molecular weights, alcohol interchange properties and N. M. R. spectra of these derivatives suggest that they are coordination compounds with tetraisopropoxyaluminate behaving as a bidentate ligand. Even the simple tetrameric aluminium isopropoxide has been shown to have the structure containing three tetraisopropoxyaluminate groups chelating a central aluminium atom.

As the nature of metal alkoxides varies with the electropositive character of the central metal atom, the formation of bi-metallic alkoxides like $K_2Be(OEt)_4$ and $KZn(OPr^i)_8$ could be simply explained on the basis of neutralisation reactions between basic and acidic alkoxides. The apparent parallelism to the formation of bimetallic hydroxo-derivatives of the type $K_2Be(OH)_4$ and $KZn(OH)_8$ led Meerwein and Bersin¹ to coin the name 'alkoxo salts' for such derivatives. These authors further concluded that the stability of these alkoxo-salts, as in the case of hydroxo salts, depends upon the electronegativity difference between the metals involved.

The preparation of a few stable double lanthanon isopropoxides, $Ln[Al(OPr^i)_4]_3$ synthesised recently² can also be explained on the above assumption that these are formed by neutralisation of basic $Ln(OPr^i)_3$, with acidic $Al(OPr^i)_3$, although volatile covalent character of the double isopropoxides did raise some doubts about the derivatives being 'alkoxo-salts' of the type $Ln^{3+}[Al(OPr^i)_4]_3$, envisaged by Meerwein and Bersin¹. The synthesis of almost equally stable double isopropoxides of gallium, $Ga[Al(OPr^i)_4]_3$ and indium, $In[Al(OPr^i)_4]_3$ with aluminium³ makes this simple acid neutralisation concept even more doubtful as gallium and indium are almost as weakly metallic as

aluminium. The work has since been extended^{4,5,6} to the synthesis of similar double isopropoxides of a variety of metals of valencies one to five. The formulae of these derivatives in the cases of mono-, bi- and tri-valent metals can be in general represented by the general formula (I).

In the case of tetravalent metals, thorium appears to give a similar derivative $Th[Al(OPr^i)_4]_4$, but zirconium (or hafnium) gives derivatives which can be represented by the general formula $(Pr^iO)_2 Zr[Al(OPr^i)_4]_2$. Similarly, niobium (or tantalum) also gives derivatives with the formula $(Pr^iO)_3 Nb[Al(OPr^i)_4]_2$. These can, therefore, be represented by the general formula

(where $n=2$, when M is Zr or Hf and
 $n=3$, when M is Nb or Ta).
(Formula II)

This coordination model for the double isopropoxides described above appears to be fully supported by synthetic and physico-chemical evidence described briefly below. In a few cases, some other derivatives (less stable than the ones described above) have also been obtained and more detailed work is being planned to establish their identity and configuration.

1. Preparation of double isopropoxides of Mono-valent metals :

When aluminium isopropoxide and alkali isopropoxides are reacted together in 1 : 1 molar ratio, double

(where n , the valency of the central metal atom M, is 1, 2 or 3)
(Formula I)

isopropoxides⁴ with the general formula $MAl(OPr^t)_4$ are obtained :

The isopropoxides of lithium and sodium are practically insoluble in isopropanol and benzene. However, potassium aluminium isopropoxide is soluble in isopropanol. On heating the double isopropoxides under reduced pressure, these appear to undergo decomposition without elimination of aluminium isopropoxide; only the potassium derivative sublimes at a bath temperature of 180-185°/0.5 mm in rather a low yield.

If the aluminium isopropoxide and alkali isopropoxides are taken in 1 : 2 molar ratio, products of the types $M_3Al_2(OPr^t)_9$ are obtained.

Formation of double isopropoxides of aluminium with alkali metals has been investigated by conductometric and potentiometric studies recently⁷ and evidence could be adduced for the formation of $MAl(OPr^t)_4$ species only.

2. Preparation of Double Isopropoxides of Bivalent Metals : In contrast to alkali isopropoxides, alkaline earth isopropoxides are insoluble in isopropanol and the dissolution of these metals in isopropanol is extremely slow probably due to the formation of a surface layer of the insoluble isopropoxides. Soluble double isopropoxides^{8,9} of aluminium with alkaline earth metals and magnesium with the general formula, $M[Al(OPr^t)_4]_2$, (where M = Mg, Ca, Sr and Ba), have been prepared by the reaction of alkaline earth metals with aluminium isopropoxide in 1 : 2 molar ratio in isopropanol. The rate of dissolution of these alkaline earth metals which is extremely slow in isopropanol appears to be accelerated by the presence of aluminium isopropoxide. Even then, in some cases catalytic amounts of mercuric chloride have to be added to increase the rate of dissolution. The overall reaction can be depicted by the following simple equation :

If the above reactions are carried out by taking the alkaline earth metals and aluminium isopropoxide in the molar ratio 1:1, a mixture of soluble $M[Al(OPr^t)_4]_2$ and insoluble $M(OPr^t)_2$ is obtained in equimolar ratio. The reaction was also carried out between strontium metal and aluminium isopropoxide in isopropanol in the molar ratio 1 : 4, when a colourless, viscous liquid was obtained after the removal of solvent. On heating this viscous liquid under reduced pressure, aluminium isopropoxide distilled off first, followed by the double isopropoxide $Sr[Al(OPr^t)_4]_2$ which distilled at a higher temperature. These reactions can, therefore, be represented as below :

These alkaline earth metal derivatives $M[Al(OPr^t)_4]_2$, are white crystalline solids except the magnesium derivative, which is a colourless liquid at the room temperature. These are soluble in isopropanol and other organic solvents. Molecular weights of these compounds were determined ebullioscopically in benzene; the magnesium derivative was found to be monomeric while the rest exhibited dimeric behaviour.

3. Preparation of Double Isopropoxides of Trivalent Metals : Mehrotra and coworkers^{2,10} synthesised a large number of volatile double isopropoxides of lanthanons and other trivalent metals. These were initially prepared by the reactions of anhydrous trichlorides of these metals with potassium aluminium isopropoxide in 1 : 3 molar ratio in isopropanol. Potassium aluminium isopropoxide was chosen for the reaction in preference to sodium aluminium isopropoxide, due to its solubility in isopropanol. The following general reaction appears to proceed with facility :

Identical products with the formula $M[Al(OPr^t)_4]_3$ were obtained by two different routes which can be represented by the following equations :

[In the preceding three equations M = Ga³, In³, Sc³, Y³(La, Pr, Nd, Sm, Dy, Yb)^{2,4}, Ho^{1,0}, Ce^{1,1}, Gd^{1,1} and Er^{1,1}]

In order to establish further the identity of the products, the last reaction between lanthanon isopropoxide and aluminium isopropoxide was repeated with excess (more than three moles) of aluminium isopropoxide. After refluxing the mixture in isopropanol, the semi-solid residue, obtained after removal of the solvent was subjected to distillation under reduced pressure. It was found that initially the excess of aluminium isopropoxide distilled out at 80-100°/1mm, followed by the double isopropoxide with the same formula, $\text{Ln}[\text{Al}(\text{OPr}^i)_4]_3$ which distilled out at a higher temperature (180-200°/1mm).

The above double alkoxides, $\text{Ln}[\text{Al}(\text{OPr}^i)_4]_3$, are soluble in organic solvents and can be distilled in almost quantitative yields under reduced pressure. Molecular weight determinations in benzene and isopropanol revealed that the experimental values correspond to the formula weight of $\text{Ln}[\text{Al}(\text{OPr}^i)_4]_3$ taken.

4. Preparation of Double Isopropoxides of Tetravalent Metals: Albers *et al.*^{1,2} in 1952 prepared a double isopropoxide of tetravalent uranium by the reaction of anhydrous uranium chloride with a gel of sodium aluminium isopropoxide in isopropanol:

The double isopropoxides of thorium and zirconium were similarly prepared³ by the reactions of ThCl_4 and $(\text{Pr}^i\text{O})_2\text{ZrCl}_2$ respectively with $\text{KAl}(\text{OPr}^i)_4$ in isopropanol in the 1:4 and 1:2 molar ratios. The reactions can be represented by the following equations:

Identical zirconium (or hafnium)^{1,3} double aluminium isopropoxides have also been synthesised by simply refluxing the two isopropoxides in the following molar ratios in isopropanol. These reactions can be represented by the following general equations:

In the last reaction, the product on distillation first gave the more volatile aluminium isopropoxide followed by the double isopropoxide which was found to correspond again to the composition $(\text{Pr}^i\text{O})_2\text{Zr}[\text{Al}(\text{OPr}^i)_4]_2$.

5. Preparation of Double Isopropoxide of Pentavalent Metals: Niobium and tantalum isopropoxides^{5,14} react with aluminium or gallium isopropoxides in the following molar ratios. Analyses of the products obtained correspond to those indicated in the following equations:

(where $\text{M} = \text{Nb}$ or Ta , $\text{M}' = \text{Al}$ or Ga)

The products $\text{MM}'(\text{OPr}^i)_8$ and $\text{MM}'_2(\text{OPr}^i)_{11}$ are colourless pastes and liquids respectively. These are all soluble in common organic solvents and can be distilled unchanged under reduced pressure.

Structural Aspects: A bridge structure (I) involving two tetra isopropoxyaluminate ligands was suggested in 1953 by Mehrotra^{1,5} for dimeric aluminium isopropoxide in the vapour phase:

(Structure I)

It was further reported^{1,5,16} that aluminium isopropoxide when freshly distilled is essentially trimeric in benzene solution, but on ageing it shows a tetrameric behaviour. Bradley^{17,18} made a novel suggestion in 1960 that the ageing of aluminium isopropoxide involves a change in coordination number of the central aluminium atom from four to six and he suggested the following interesting structure (II) for tetrameric aluminium isopropoxide in which the central aluminium atom is chelated by three bidentate tetraisopropoxy-

aluminate groups :

(Structure II)

The above structure was supported by its measurements on N.M.R. spectra in different solvents by Shiner *et. al.*¹⁹ in 1963. Three sets of doublets of methyl proton peaks were observed. The area of the upfield doublet was equal to the area of the two lowfield doublets which were found to be equal in themselves. The appearance of upfield doublet and the lowfield doublets in the N.M.R. spectrum was explained to be due to the methyl protons of the six-terminal and six-bridged isopropoxy groups respectively. Shiner *et. al.*¹⁹ explained the presence of two lowfield doublets due to the non-interchangeability of the isopropoxy groups attached to the central aluminium atom. Therefore, the methyl groups appear to be in a fixed orientation which may be approximately equatorial or axial to the plane of aluminium atoms.

Huckerby *et. al.*²⁰ explained in 1968 the existence of two low field doublets in the bridged isopropoxy groups in the NMR spectrum of the tetrameric aluminium isopropoxide to be due to the asymmetry of the bridging central aluminium atom.

Mehrotra and coworkers⁹ have also observed three sets of doublets in the ratio of 1 : 1 : 1 : 1 : 2 : 2 in the NMR spectra which again confirmed the tetrameric structure proposed for aluminium isopropoxide. The positions of the methyl proton peaks observed in the NMR spectra at room temperature in cycles per second can be depicted as below :

Solvent	A	B	C	D	E	F	Machine
CCl ₄	91	85	80	74	69	63	A60
CDCl ₃	93	87	82	76	71	65	A60
CCl ₄	152	145	133	128	127	121	HA100

In the HA-100 spectrum of aluminium isopropoxide, two distinct septet sets of peaks with equal area have also been observed for the first time. The presence of

these peaks could be explained to be due to the methine protons of the terminal and bridging isopropoxy groups. Huckerby *et. al.*²⁰ predicted that if the splitting of the methyl protons in the spectra of some of the isopropoxides be explained in terms of magnetic non-equivalence of the two methyls on the same isopropoxy groups, then the corresponding methine protons on all the isopropoxy groups in similar conditions should remain identical. This general conclusion was confirmed by the presence of only two sets of peaks of equal areas. If the explanation given by Shiner *et. al.*¹⁹ were accepted three sets of peaks could have been expected for the methine protons in the spectrum.

Volatile double isopropoxides of lanthanons, Ln[Al(OPrⁱ)₄]₃ were also assigned tentatively a similar structure (III) by Mehrotra and Agarwal² :

(Structure III)

The above structure appeared to receive support by alcoholysis experiments with tertiary alcohols. Most of the metal alkoxides undergo interchange reactions with facility when refluxed with other alcohols. For example, aluminium isopropoxide is changed to aluminium butoxide and pentoxide when refluxed with excess of n-butanol or n-pentanol. However, with ramified tertiary alcohols, two of the three isopropoxy groups per aluminium metal are readily replaced but the replacement of the third group is extremely slow and does not appear to proceed with tertiary pentanol at all^{15,16}. Compared to aluminium alkoxides, the alcoholysis of lanthanon alkoxides is extremely slow²¹. The interchange of Ho[Al(OPrⁱ)₄]₃ with excess tertiary butanol and pentanol¹⁰ appears to become extremely slow after the replacement of about eight and six groups of isopropanol respectively. In view of the relative ease of alcoholysis of aluminium alkoxides, it is plausible to assume that the replacement mainly occurs at the aluminium atoms in these double alkoxides also. The replacement of bridged isopropoxy groups appears to be hindered sterically in the case of these highly ramified alcohols. It may be on account of this reason that the interchangeability appears to become negligible after the aluminium atoms are surrounded by one isopropoxy and three tertiary butoxy groups or two isopropoxy and two tertiary pentoxy groups respec-

tively as shown in the following structures (IV) & (V) :

(Structure IV)

(Structure V)

The N. M. R. spectrum of the $\text{La}[\text{Al}(\text{OPr}^i)_4]_3$ gave only one single methyl doublet, centred around 1.48 ppm downfield from tetramethyl silane. Worrall and coworkers²² suggested the occurrence of a single methyl doublet in the spectrum to be due to ready interchangeability of terminal and isopropoxy groups. In fact, they could not succeed in resolving the peak even by cooling the solution to -60° . However, they confirmed the structure proposed for $\text{La}[\text{Al}(\text{OPr}^i)_4]_3$

The Mass spectrum of $\text{La}[\text{Al}(\text{OPr}^i)_4]_3$

Mass No.	I	Mass No.	I
928 (tetramer)	7	504	13
913	5	489	8
869	100	461	40
854	50	446	11
767	62	402	29
752	17	387	8
665	46	345	10
650	8	300	9
591	5	170	14
563	33	106	21
548	18	106	

by Mehrotra and Agarwal²⁰ with the help of mass spectroscopic study which is given in the table.

Mehrotra and coworkers^{23,24} in 1972 studied the N. M. R. spectra of $\text{Y}[\text{Al}(\text{OPr}^i)_4]_3$ and $\text{Pr}[\text{Al}(\text{OPr}^i)_4]_3$, which also exhibited the presence of a single doublet. The peaks of $\text{Y}[\text{Al}(\text{OPr}^i)_4]_3$ and $\text{Pr}[\text{Al}(\text{OPr}^i)_4]_3$ were found to be at 1.25 ppm downfield and 3.22 ppm upfield respectively from tetramethylsilane. The shift of the position of the peak in the case of praseodymium can be suggested to be due to the paramagnetic nature of this metal.

The N.M.R. spectrum²⁴ of $\text{Yb}[\text{Al}(\text{OPr}^i)_4]_3$ showed the presence of a very weak peak at 1.19 ppm. downfield from tetramethylsilane. However, two broad peaks centred at 5.56 and 7.10 ppm upfield from tetramethylsilane were also obtained. The area of these peaks was found on integration to be in the ratio of 6 : 1, indicating that these could be assigned to methyl and methine protons respectively, but both are contact shifted due to the paramagnetic nature of ytterbium. On cooling the solution to -35° , further contact shift appears to occur. The peak at 7.1 ppm due to methine protons seems to be shifted to 8.8 ppm. However, the peak at 5.56 ppm. due to methyl protons appears to be resolved into two peaks of almost equal area centred at 5.6 and 7.1 ppm. The total area of these two peaks is again approximately six times the area of the peak at 8.8 ppm. This suggests the presence of two types of isopropoxy groups in the molecule, $\text{Yb}[\text{Al}(\text{OPr}^i)_4]_3$, in almost equal numbers (six terminal and six bridging isopropoxy groups).

An obvious explanation for the appearance of only one type of methyl protons in the spectra of $\text{La}[\text{Al}(\text{OPr}^i)_4]_3$, and $\text{Pr}[\text{Al}(\text{OPr}^i)_4]_3$ has been suggested to be the free exchange of terminal and bridging isopropoxy groups due to the large radius of the central lanthanide element. In view of the above, it was considered worthwhile to synthesise and record the N.M.R. spectrum of $\text{Lu}[\text{Al}(\text{OPr}^i)_4]_3$, as lutecium has the smallest radius of all the lanthanon atoms and is diamagnetic in its +3 state. In the case of $\text{Lu}[\text{Al}(\text{OPr}^i)_4]_3$, the presence of two types of isopropoxy groups, bridged and terminal, in equal numbers is observed even at the room temperature. The peaks observed are found at 2.76, 2.56, 2.20, 2.03 ppm downfield from tetramethylsilane. The peaks due to methine protons were observed at 8.45 and 8.33 ppm. The ratio of the area of methyl and methine protons was found to be 6 : 1.

N. M. R spectrum^{23,24} of $\text{Sc}[\text{Al}(\text{OPr}^i)_4]_3$ was found to be almost identical to the spectrum of tetrameric aluminium isopropoxides, suggesting a similar structure (VI) for $\text{Sc}[\text{Al}(\text{OPr}^i)_4]_3$ also. The

structure can be represented as below :

(Structure VI)

The positions of methyl protons peaks obtained in the N. M. R. spectrum of $\text{Sc}[\text{Al}(\text{OPr}^i)_4]_3$ in cycles per second from tetramethylsilane are given below :

Solvent	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	Machine
CCl_4	151	145	135	129	115	109	112	106	HA 100
CCl_4	90	84	81	75	68	62	67	61	A 60
CDCl_3	95	89	85	79	73	67	72	66	A 66

However, in the case of $\text{Sc}[\text{Al}(\text{OPr}^i)_4]_3$, it has been observed that the peaks due to methyl protons of the terminal isopropoxy groups also show splitting, giving two closely lying doublets of almost equal area. This splitting of the methyl protons of the terminal isopropoxy groups can also be explained to be due to magnetic non-equivalence of the methyl proton even in the non-bridging isopropoxy as was observed in the case of bridging isopropoxy groups. The N. M. R. spectra of $\text{In}[\text{Al}(\text{OPr}^i)_4]_3$ and $\text{In}[\text{Ga}(\text{OPr}^i)_4]_3$ have also been recorded by Mehrotra and Mehrotra^{2,3,4}. The structure (VII) & (VIII) of these compounds also appears to correspond to that of tetrameric aluminium isopropoxide and can be represented as below :

(Structure VII)

(Structure VIII)

The spectrum of $\text{In}[\text{Al}(\text{OPr}^i)_4]_3$ when run on a HA 10J machine was found to be similar to that of $\text{Sc}[\text{Al}(\text{OPr}^i)_4]_3$. The peaks due to the terminal isopropoxy groups also show splitting.

METHYL PROTON PEAKS OF THE ISOPROPOXIDES IN CYCLES PER SECOND AT 60 MHZ FROM TETRAMETHYLSILANE AT ROOM TEMPERATURE

Compound	Solvent	A	B	C	D	E	F
$\text{In}[\text{Al}(\text{OPr}^i)_4]_3$	CCl_4	91	85	81	75	69	63
$\text{In}[\text{Al}(\text{OPr}^i)_4]_3$	CDCl_3	91	85	81	75	69	63
$\text{In}[\text{Ga}(\text{OPr}^i)_4]_3$	CDCl_3	91	85	83	77	73	67

In view of the identical covalent radii (1.44 Å) for scandium and indium, this observed similarity in the spectra of $\text{Sc}[\text{Al}(\text{OPr}^i)_4]_3$ and $\text{In}[\text{Al}(\text{OPr}^i)_4]_3$ can be easily understood.

METHYL PROTON PEAKS IN THE NMR SPECTRA OF $\text{In}[\text{Al}(\text{OPr}^i)_4]_3$ IN CYCLES PER SECOND FROM TETRAMETHYLSILANE AT ROOM TEMPERATURE

Solvent	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
CCl_4	151	145	135	129	116	110	114	108
CDCl_3	151	145	135	129	116	110	114	104

The structure (IX) of double alkali aluminium isopropoxide, $\text{MAl}(\text{OPr}^i)_4$ (where M = Li, Na or K), was suggested by Mehrotra and Mehrotra¹¹ (1971) and can be represented as below :

(Structure IX)

The tendency of formation of above type derivatives appears to depend upon the solvation with isopropanol molecules. It may be that this solvation is facilitated by increasing size of the alkali atom from lithium through sodium to potassium, increasing the solubility of these derivatives respectively.

The structure (X) of alkaline earth aluminium double isopropoxides⁶ (monomeric form) can be depicted as below :

(Structure X)

(where M = Mg, Ca, Sr or Ba)

Evidence for this structure is given by the interchangeability of only six out of eight isopropoxy groups by tertiary butoxy groups, when the double isopropoxide is refluxed even with a large excess of tertiary butanol accompanied by continuous fractionation of the lower alcohol formed in the alcoholysis reaction. The structure of this zirconium dialuminium diisopropoxide hexatertiary butoxide can be represented as below (XI) :

(Structure XI)

On the basis of molecular complexity and the presence of bridging and non-bridging isopropoxy

groups in I. R. spectra, Agarwal⁴ proposed the following structure (XII) for monomeric $Zr[Al_2(OPr^i)_{10}]$. In this compound, four isopropoxy groups occupy terminal positions on aluminium atoms, two occupy terminal positions on zirconium and the remaining four isopropoxy groups form bridges.

(Structure XII)

Similarly the structure of $HfAl_2(OPr^t)_{10}$ appears to receive support from alcoholysis measurements and N.M.R. study. Mehrotra and Mehrotra¹³ carried out the alcoholysis reaction of $HfAl_2(OPr^t)_{10}$ with excess tertiary butanol. Only six out of the ten isopropoxy groups replaced with butoxy groups, giving rise to the following type of structure (XIII) for the product, $HfAl_2(OPr^t)_4(OBu^t)_6$.

(Structure XIII)

The N.M.R. spectra of $HfAl_2(OPr^t)_{10}$ in carbon tetrachloride exhibited peaks at 140, 134, 124, 118, 114 and 108 ppm having area ratio 2 : 2, 1 : 1 and 2 : 2 which indicates three types of isopropoxy groups confirming structure (XIV) of the compound $HfAl_2(OPr^t)_{10}$.

(Structure XIV)

On the similar above grounds, the structure (XV) for the derivatives $MM'_2(OPr^i)_{11}$ (where $M=Nb$ or Ta and $M'=Al$ or Ga) could be suggested^{6,14} as below in which niobium or tantalum atom is 7-coordinated and the aluminium atoms are 4-coordinated.

(Structure XV)

The N.M.R. spectra^{6,14} of $NbAl(OPr^i)_8$ (monomeric) in carbon tetrachloride exhibited three doublets of methyl protons in the ratio 1 : 1 : 2 indicating the presence of three types of isopropoxy groups (four terminal groups at niobium, two terminal ones at aluminium and remaining two form bridges) which confirms structure (XVI) of this compound and can be depicted as below :

(Structure XVI)

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